

WASTE-TO-BIOFUELS: VALORIZATION OF FOOD RESIDUE BIOMASS (FORBI) FOR HYDROGEN AND METHANE PRODUCTION

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Abstract

This research work concerns the production of Hydrogen and Methane from a Food Residue Biomass (FORBI) product, generated from pre-sorted Fermentable Household Food Waste in a Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR). FORBI is generated by drying and shredding the fermentable fraction of household food waste, collected door-to-door in the Municipality of Halandri, Greece.

Hydrogen production from FORBI through anaerobic fermentation under acidogenic mesophilic conditions was carried out using a 4L CSTR (H₂-CSTR), operated at 4 hr and 3 hr Hydraulic Retention Times (HRT), with a feed concentration of 15 g TS/L. Volatile fatty acids (VFAs), Total and Volatile Suspended Solids (TSS and VSS), Total and Soluble Chemical Oxygen Demand (tCOD and sCOD), Total and Dissolved Carbohydrates, pH and hydrogen content in the biogas were monitored. The H₂-CSTR operated for 32 days. During its operation, the biogas productivity reached 7.78 L/d, out of which 4.13 L/d was hydrogen (60%). This corresponds to a yield of 22 L_{biogas}/kg_{FORBI}.

The conversion of FORBI into methane was carried out through the operation of a CSTR (CH₄-CSTR) with working volume 4L (CH₄-CSTR). The reactor operated under mesophilic methanogenic conditions at 20, 15 and 10 days HRT and an organic loading of 15 g TS/L. TSS, VSS, tCOD, sCOD, pH, alkalinity, VFAs and methane content in the biogas were monitored. The mean methane percentage in the biogas was up to 65%, with an average biogas productivity of 0.5 L_{biogas}/L_{reactor}/day, during the optimum operational conditions. The biogas productivity corresponds to a productivity of 477 L_{biogas}/kg_{FORBI}.

The experimental results obtained were used as a basis for the development of a model by using AQUASIM [1] software, which was able to adequately simulate the operation of the bioreactors.

Conclusively, FORBI was proved as a suitable feedstock material both for hydrogen and methane production, resulting in high biogas yields in both cases.

1- INTRODUCTION

The recent urbanization trends throughout the world are expected to lead to a dramatic increase in the Municipal Solid Waste generation [2]. The most promising, in terms of valorization opportunities, and in the same time less exploited fraction is the biodegradable MSW. The quantity of the biodegradable MSW corresponds to a 30-50% of the total MSW quantities generated, and dramatically up to 95% is ultimately landfilled [3]. The lack of sufficient management and valorization of the generated food waste leads to high freshwater and fossil fuels consumption, as well as methane and CO₂ emissions from the decomposition processes, enhancing global warming [4]. Hence, the need to develop and apply innovative and environmentally sound valorization alternatives is urgent.

In the Municipality of Halandri [5], in Attica, Greece an innovative food waste valorization approach was developed and implemented in pilot-scale within the framework of the Horizon2020 project WASTE4think [6]. The waste management scheme implemented includes the source-separated collection of the kitchen waste from 250 households. The kitchen waste collected, was then led to a drying/shredding facility, located within the Municipality. The drying/shredding process of the food waste leads to a homogenized biomass product called FORBI (Food Residue Biomass). FORBI, apart from its homogeneity, has a variety of benefits compared to the raw food waste: its volume and weight is reduced by up to 80% in comparison with the starting kitchen waste and odours are removed, while it can be stored for prolonged periods without deteriorating.

The potential of a wide range of potential valorisation alternatives is being currently examined. The current working paper focuses on the potential generation of gaseous biofuels, namely biohydrogen and biomethane. There are numerous research works focusing on the anaerobic generation and dark fermentation of food waste [7]–[16]. However, the idea of using previously dried and shredded food waste as feedstock for these processes, is not yet widely explored.

This paper is focusing on the operational parameters optimization of the dark fermentation and anaerobic digestion processes of FORBI. Moreover, the ADM1 modeling framework was used to develop a model adequately describing the anaerobic digestion process[17].

2- MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Analytical methods

Determination of soluble (sCOD) and total chemical oxygen demand (tCOD), total (TSS) and volatile (VSS) suspended solids, total alkalinity and temperature were carried out according to Standard Methods [18]. The pH was measured using a digital pH-meter (WTW INOLAB PH720). The biogas production rate was measured using an oil displacement technique [19]. For the quantification of VFAs, 1 mL of sample acidified with 30 µL of 20% H₂SO₄ was analyzed on a gas chromatograph (Shimadzu GC-2010), equipped with a flame ionization detector and a capillary column (Agilent technologies, INC. 30 m 0.53 mm). The oven was programmed from 105 to 160°C at a rate of 15°C/min, and subsequently to 235°C (held for 3 min) at a rate of 20°C/min. Helium was used as the carrier gas at 15 mL/min, the injector temperature was set at 175°C and the detector at 225°C. The produced hydrogen and methane were quantified with a gas chromatograph (Shimadzu GC-2014), equipped with a thermal conductivity detector and a 12390-U SUPELCO Metal Packed GC Column. Helium and Argon were used as carrier gases for the measurement of methane and hydrogen respectively.

2.2. Feedstock

FORBI is produced through drying and shredding of food waste using a GAIA GC-300 food waste dryer. The main characteristics of FORBI are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 main characteristics of FORBI

Ingredient	% w/w (In dry base)
Proteins	13.70±0.44
Lipids	12.26±0.11
Glucose	0.00
Sucrose	0.51±0.04
Total reducing sugars	4.96±0.94
Starch	10.68±0.07
Pectin	3.27±0.082
Cellulose	10.31±0.07
Hemicellulose	11.32±0.17
Lignin	6.75±0.15
Ash	7.16±0.27

2.3. Experiments for hydrogen production

A Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor (H_2 -CSTR) with a working volume of 4L was used for the assessment of use of FORBI as feedstock for the production of biohydrogen through dark fermentation. The H_2 -CSTR was made of stainless steel and the temperature control (35 ± 0.5 °C) was achieved via recirculation of warm water in the outer jacket of the bioreactor. The H_2 -CSTR operated under anaerobic conditions at different Hydraulic Retention Times (HRTs) (4 and 3 hours). During start-up, the CSTR was inoculated with 4 L of thermally treated (100 °C for 20 minutes) activated sludge. The thermal pretreatment is necessary for the inhibition of methanogens and domination of hydrogen producing microorganisms such as bacteria belonging to the class of Clostridia [20]. The H_2 -CSTR was fed using a peristaltic pump with an aquatic suspension of FORBI (15g FORBI/L) operating in continuous mode. The tCOD of the feedstock was 17.6 g/L on the average. The dark fermentation experimental procedure lasted 35 days. During day 25 of the experimental procedure 50 ml of methanogens from the CH_4 -CSTR were added to the bioreactor in order to test whether the reactor can stably overcome methanogen contamination. Throughout the operation of the H_2 -CSTR no pH regulation took place and the pH remained stable at 4.6- 4.7.

During the experimental procedure, gas and liquid samples were taken regularly to measure biogas composition, TSS, VSS, pH, VFAs, soluble and total COD.

2.4 Experiments for methane production

A conventional CSTR-type bioreactor (CH₄- CSTR) was used to investigate the methane production potential of FORBI. The anaerobic digestion experimental procedure lasted 202 days, including three different phases based on the operational parameters. During the first phase (days 1-138) the HRT was set to 19.3 days, while the tCOD of the feedstock was 17.6 g/L on the average. After steady state was reached, the HRT was reduced to 14.9 days, while the inflow tCOD was essentially the same (16.9 g/L on the average). This second phase lasted 51 days. Finally, the HRT was reduced to 10 days (the inflow tCOD was again 16.5 g/L on the average). This last phase of the experimental procedure lasted for 14 days, before the process failed with biogas production and pH dropping due to VFA accumulation.

During the experimental procedure, gas and liquid samples were taken regularly to measure biogas production rate, TSS, VSS, VFAs, pH, Alkalinity, soluble and total COD.

2.5 Mathematical simulation

The experimental results from (CH₄- CSTR) were used as the basis for developing a mathematical model. AQUASIM 2.0 was used to develop the model.

3- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 H₂-CSTR

The biogas productivity and the composition of the biogas produced by the H₂-CSTR are given in Figures 1 and 2, respectively. The bioreactor operated in continuous mode immediately after the inoculation of the bioreactor. During the first four days the biogas productivity and the percentage of hydrogen increased steeply and then remained almost stable for 18 days. During this 18-days period of operation, an average biogas productivity rate of 1.15 L_{biogas}/L_{bioreactor}/day was achieved, which corresponds to 0.0129 L_{biogas}/g_{FORBI} (in wet base). The mean percentage of hydrogen during this period was equal to 49.4% while it reached up to 59%, indicating a robust, stable, long-term operation over time. The mean removal of soluble carbohydrates was 57.7% (Data not shown). Iso-valeric, iso-butyric and valeric acids were produced in small quantities. As presented in Fig. 3, the dominant metabolic products were butyric and acetic acid. This observation verified that the hydrogen production was related to the production of butyrate and acetate [reactions (1) and (2)] [20]. The low concentrations of propionic acid (Fig. 3) indicate an efficient hydrogen production process, as the formation of propionate consumes hydrogen [reaction (3)] [21].

In order to test the sustainability of the bioreactor, we intentionally contaminated the H₂-CSTR with methanogens by feeding 50 ml of the mixed culture from the anaerobic CH₄- CSTR. We have shown (unpublished data) that the production of hydrogen can be significantly impaired by the domination

of hydrogen consuming methanogens. Despite the fact that the methanogens that are added to the H₂-CSTR cannot be “washed-out”, as methane is produced-even in low quantities- (Fig. 2), the biogas productivity of the bioreactor remained stable and the percentage of hydrogen high.

The operation of the H₂-CSTR with even lower HRT, equal to 3 hours, led to an increase of biogas productivity, whereas the percentage of hydrogen remained stable. During this period of operation, an average biogas productivity rate of 1.505 L_{biogas}/L_{bioreactor}/day was achieved, which corresponds to 0.0125 L_{biogas}/g_{FORBI} (on wet basis). In addition to this, the amount of produced VFAs decreased (Fig.3). Therefore, despite the fact that the decrease of HRT led to the increase of biogas productivity, the operation of H₂-CSTR with an HRT of 3 hours was not investigated further as the biogas productivity per gram of feedstock decreased substantially.

Figure 1. Biogas productivity by H₂-CSTR during its operation.

Figure 2. Composition of the biogas produced by the H₂-CSTR during its operation.

Figure 3. Production of VFAs during the operation of H_2 -CSTR.

3.2 CH_4 -CSTR

The methane production process worked smoothly throughout the experimental procedure. During the first experimental phase (HRT=19.3 d) an average biogas productivity rate of 0.303 L/L_{bioreactor}/day was achieved, which corresponds to 0.382 L_{biogas}/g_{FORBI}, while the mean methane content of the biogas was up to 65%.

During the second experimental phase (HRT= 14.9 days) the biogas productivity rate increased to 0.451 L/L_{bioreactor}/day, which in turn corresponds to 0.467L_{biogas}/g_{FORBI}. The average methane content of the biogas produced during phase 2 was 62%.

Finally, the HRT decrease to 9.77 days led to process failure. More specifically, the concentration of Volatile Fatty Acids increased gradually, as shown in Figure 2.

The most important experimental results for the methane production are presented in Figures 4 & 5:

Figure 4 For all the three experimental phases of the Anaerobic Digestion process, biogas productivity rate is presented.

Figure 5 For all the three experimental phases of the Anaerobic Digestion process, the metabolic products concentration is presented. The sharp increase of the concentration during the final -third- phase of the procedure indicates process failure.

Aquasim modeling with ADM1

Based on the experimental results obtained throughout the experimental process, an ADM1 model was developed for the simulation of the process. The modeling results are presented in Figs. 6-12:

Figure 6 Biogas productivity experimental data and model simulation

Figure 7 pH experimental data and model simulation

Figure 8 sCOD experimental data and model simulation

Figure 9 Acetic acid experimental data and model simulation

Figure 10 Butyric Acid experimental data and model simulation

Figure 11 Propionic acid experimental data and model simulation

Figure 12 Volatile Suspended Solids

The model is adequately simulating the experimental process. The deviation observed during the first 70 days between the experimental data and the modeling outcome in sCOD and VSS, is probably related to the time needed for the process to reach steady-state conditions, given the fact that the initial reactor state was not sufficiently known..

4- CONCLUSIONS

The present work investigated the potential valorization of FORBI, an innovative biomass product, for the production of gaseous biofuels, methane and hydrogen. FORBI was generated by drying and shredding of pre-sorted door-to-door collected household kitchen waste in the Municipality of

Halandri. The development and implementation of the specific bio-waste management scheme aspires to revolutionize the way the Fermentable Municipal Solid Waste is being managed. Hydrogen productivity using FORBI as feedstock reached 1.15 L_{biogas}/L_{bioreactor}/day with an HRT of 4 hours. The mean percentage of hydrogen during this period was 49.4%. Methane productivity through FORBI, using a conventional CSTR, reached a productivity of 0.467 L_{biogas}/g_{FORBI} with an HRT of 15 days. The mean methane content of the biogas produced was 62%. The anaerobic digestion process failed when the HRT was decreased to 10 days. An ADM-1 model was developed -using AQUASIM-based on the experimental results of the anaerobic digestion process. The modelling of the process was satisfactory.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Reichert P., *AQUASIM—A tool for simulation and data analysis of aquatic systems*, vol. 30. (1994).
- [2] Hoornweg D. and Bhada-Tata P., “What a Waste: A Global Review of Solid Waste Management,” *Urban Dev. Ser. Knowl. Pap. no.15, World Bank*, p. 116, (2012).
- [3] Michalopoulos I., Lytras G. M., Papadopoulou K., A. Goumenos, I. Zacharopoulos, C. Lytras, and G. Lyberatos, “Hydrogen and Methane Production from Food Residue Biomass Product (FORBI),” in *15th International Conference on Environmental Science and Technology*, no. September, pp. 1–5 (2017).
- [4] Hall K. D., Guo J., Dore M., and Chow C. C., “The progressive increase of food waste in America and its environmental impact,” *PLoS One*, vol. 4, no. 11, pp. 9–14, (2009).
- [5] Municipality of Halandri, “Municipality of Halandri,” *Municipality of Halandri Official Website*, (2014).
- [6] WASTE4Think, “Moving towards Life cycle Thinking by integrating Advanced Waste Management Systems,” (2015).
- [7] Zhang Z., O’Hara I. M., Mundree S., Gao B., Ball A. S., Zhu N., Bai Z., and Jin B., “Biofuels from food processing wastes,” *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.*, vol. 38, pp. 97–105, (2016).
- [8] Martinez J., Dabert, P. Barrington S., and C. Burton, “Livestock waste treatment systems for environmental quality, food safety, and sustainability,” *Bioresour. Technol.*, vol. 100, no. 22, pp. 5527–5536, (2009).
- [9] Nghiem L. D., K. Koch, D. Bolzonella, and J. E. Drewes, “Full scale co-digestion of wastewater sludge and food waste: Bottlenecks and possibilities,” *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 72, no. January, pp. 354–362, (2017).
- [10] Liu X., X. Gao, W. Wang, L. Zheng, Y. Zhou, and Y. Sun, “Pilot-scale anaerobic co-digestion of municipal biomass waste: Focusing on biogas production and GHG reduction,” *Renew. Energy*, vol. 44, no. August, pp. 463–468, (2012).
- [11] Gray D., P. Suto, and C. Peck, “Anaerobic Digestion of Food Waste,” *U.S. Environ. Plan. Agency*

Reg. 9, no. March, (2008).

- [12] Luque R. and J. H. Clark, "Valorisation of food residues: waste to wealth using green chemical technologies," *Sustain. Chem. Process.*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 10, (2013).
- [13] Zhang R., H. M. El-Mashad, K. Hartman, F. Wang, G. Liu, C. Choate, and P. Gamble, "Characterization of food waste as feedstock for anaerobic digestion," *Bioresour. Technol.*, vol. 98, no. 4, pp. 929–935, (2007).
- [14] Koch K., B. Helmreich, and J. E. Drewes, "Co-digestion of food waste in municipal wastewater treatment plants: Effect of different mixtures on methane yield and hydrolysis rate constant," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 137, pp. 250–255, (2015).
- [15] Kim D. H., S. H. Kim, and H. S. Shin, "Hydrogen fermentation of food waste without inoculum addition," *Enzyme Microb. Technol.*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 181–187, (2009).
- [16] Nathao C., U. Sirisukpoka, and N. Pisutpaisal, "Production of hydrogen and methane by one and two stage fermentation of food waste," *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 38, no. 35, pp. 15764–15769, (2013).
- [17] Batstone D. J., J. Keller, and I. Angelidaki, "Anaerobic digestion model No. 1," *Water Sci. Technol.*, vol. 45, no. 10, pp. 65–73, (2002).
- [18] APHA/AWWA/WEF, "Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater," *Stand. Methods*, p. 541, (2012).
- [19] Skiadas I. V and G. Lyberatos, "The periodic anaerobic baffled reactor," *Water Sci. Technol.*, vol. 38, no. 8, pp. 401–408, (1998).
- [20] Antonopoulou G., H. N. Gavala, I. V Skiadas, K. Angelopoulos, and G. Lyberatos, "Biofuels generation from sweet sorghum: Fermentative hydrogen production and anaerobic digestion of the remaining biomass," *Bioresour. Technol.*, vol. 99, no. 1, pp. 110–119, (2008).
- [21] Sivagurunathan P., B. Sen, and C.-Y. Lin, "High-rate fermentative hydrogen production from beverage wastewater," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 147, pp. 1–9, (2015).